

Long-duration storm surges due to 2023 successive UK storms Ciarán and Domingos: Generation, field surveys, and numerical modelling

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ABSTRACT

We model the long-duration storm surges generated by October–November 2023 storm chain in the English Channel employing a hybrid method including numerical modelling, field surveys and analysis of oceanic and atmospheric data. The event consisted of three successive storms: a weaker unnamed storm (27–30 October), Storm Ciarán (2–3 November with minimum pressure 948 hPa) and Storm Domingos (4–5 November with minimum pressure 958 hPa). The average surge duration produced by this storm chain was 10.5 days. The average maximum air pressure drop was 42 hPa during Ciarán and 23 hPa during Domingos. These pressure drops, combined with onshore wind stresses, led to average maximum storm surge amplitudes of 92 cm for Ciarán and 74 cm for Domingos. We accurately modelled storm surges using a three-level nested grid system and validated the results with tide gauge data. Sensitivity analysis showed a spatially-dependant impacts from tides and waves on maximum surge amplitudes. To correlate our modelling and data analysis with actual conditions on the ground, field surveys were conducted where we measured a runup heights of 4.1 m in Chesil Beach and 2.1 m in West Bay. These values were successfully reproduced by two independent empirical runup models enabling adaption of suitable models for storm hazard mitigation and resilience. A meteotsunami with an amplitude of 17–23 cm and a period of 11–40 min was identified during Ciarán. The innovative hybrid framework developed in this study is recommended for building robust systems for storm warnings and coastal resilience.

1. Introduction

Southern coasts of the UK were severely affected by a chain of three consecutive storms in October and November 2023. The largest of these three storm systems was Storm Ciarán which was active in the UK, Channel Islands, France and other countries in late October and early November 2023 (Fig. 1). Ciarán, named by UK's Met Office (2023) on 29th October 2023, approached the UK from west–southwest, moving along the English Channel. Ciarán achieved an exceptionally low air pressure of 953.3 hPa (947.9 hPa based on our analysis) in Plymouth (England), and a maximum wind speed of 196 km/h in Ile de Batz (France) (Met Office, 2023). According to media reports, Ciarán was responsible for at least 21 deaths across several European countries (UK, France, Italy, and others). For comparison, the previous historical UK

November low pressure record of 959.7 hPa occurred in Teignmouth (south England) in November 1916 (Met Office, 2023), more than 100 years ago. This may indicate that Ciarán was a one-in-hundred-years storm. In terms of wind speed, Ciarán is comparable to the October 1987 UK storm, which registered a maximum gust of 185 km/h with 18 fatalities (Burt and Mansfield, 1988; Met Office, 2023).

Following Storm Ciarán, the region was hit by another storm named as Domingos (Fig. 1) which was active over the Atlantic Ocean and English Channel in the period 3–5 November 2023 and was named by the Spanish Met Service (AEMET) (<https://www.aemet.es/>) (Kelly, 2023). However, the UK Met Office did not name it. Domingos was not as destructive as Ciarán but it complicated the recovery operations in the aftermath of Ciarán (Le Monde, 2023). In addition to Storms Ciarán and Domingos, another low-pressure system, not named by the UK Met

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Fig. 1. Map showing the track of the November 2023 Storms Ciarán (red circles) and Domingos (blue circles) across the Atlantic Ocean, the UK and the Europe. The air pressure gauges (blue diamonds) and tide gauge stations (orange triangles) used in this study are marked along with field survey points (pink circles). Abbreviations are: SSM (Scilly St Mary's), SLV (Silverbridge), SAL (Sefton Avenue Lipton), WCV (Woodlands Court Weather), JER (Jersey), WFN (Winfrith Newburgh), WRW (Wareham Weather), BH6 (BH6 weather), SRV (Surtainville), BNO (Benoit), NCR (Newchurch), OFP (Old Portsmouth Froggit), RMW (Ratton Manor Weather), SDW (Sidley Weather), DVT (Dover Town), and ESD (East Studdal).

Office, crossed the Atlantic Ocean impacting the English Channel around 27–30 October 2023 (prior to Ciarán). Therefore, three low-pressure storm systems have been active over the English Channel from 27th October to 6th November 2023 among which Ciarán was the most powerful and destructive one (Fig. 1). This research is focused on the analysis of the generation and impacts of storm surges and ocean waves during these three storms (particularly the stronger two events: Ciarán and Domingos) along the coasts of the UK.

South coasts of the UK are vulnerable to severe storm surges. Haigh et al. (2017) listed 329 coastal flooding events from 1915 to 2016 along the coasts of the UK. Out of the 53 most severe events ranked Category 3 or higher, 33 events impacted south coasts of the UK. The most damaging event in the past decade, involving six storms, took place during January–February 2014 (Category 4, according to Haigh et al., 2017), resulting in billions of pounds in economic losses and a few fatalities across the UK (Met Office, 2014; Masselink et al., 2016; Haigh et al., 2017; Adams and Heidarzadeh, 2021, 2023). The February 2014 storms destroyed the Dawlish railway leading to a two-month line closure and an economic loss of £1.2 billion for the southwest UK (Adams and Heidarzadeh, 2023). Other significant storms of the past

decade were Storms Ciara and Dennis, which occurred successively in February 2020 with a few days interval between them, killing a few people and causing widespread disruption across the UK (Met Office, 2020a,b).

Investigating the generation and propagation of storms, as well as impacts of the associated surges and ocean waves is essential for developing our understanding of these hazardous events. In addition, insights from the extended impacts of the three successive storms will be valuable in the ongoing effort to develop mitigation strategies and storm-resilient coastlines. The primary objective of this research is to provide a holistic analysis of the event, from its onset (generation of the storm systems along the North America coasts), growth (propagation over the Atlantic), and culmination in continuous storm surges along the southern coast of the UK. Our research improves the existing scientific basis for developing mitigation measures and enhancing resilience to coastal destructive hazards. This research builds on several previous studies of coastal flooding in the UK (Haigh et al., 2016, 2017; Swindles et al., 2018; Hendry et al., 2019; Jenkins et al., 2023; Camus et al., 2024) and complements these studies by introducing a detailed hybrid analysis approach consisting of storm tracking, numerical ocean modelling,

Table 1

The list of atmospheric air pressure and wind stations whose data are used in this study. WOW stands for the Met Office's Weather Observations Website. Wunderground refers to the weather data website: <https://www.wunderground.com/>. These stations are shown in Fig. 1.

No.	Air pressure station name (Name acronym)	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Sampling interval (min)	Source
1	Scilly St Mary's (SSM)	-6.301	49.913	60	WOW
2	Silverbridge (SLV)	-5.3808	50.1094	5	WOW
3	Sefton Avenue Lipton (SAL)	-4.1175	50.3804	5	WOW
4	Woodlands Court Weather (WCW)	-3.4031	50.6405	5	WOW
5	Jersey (JER)	-2.1955	49.2079	5	WOW
6	Surtainville (SRV)	-1.81	49.47	5	Wunderground
7	Benoit (BNO)	-1.61	49.62	5	Wunderground
8	Winfrith Newburgh (WFN)	-2.2771	50.6648	5	WOW
9	Wareham Weather (WRW)	-2.1129	50.6871	5	WOW
10	BH6 weather (BH6)	-1.8123	50.7306	5	WOW
11	Newchurch (NCR)	-1.2004	50.6618	5	WOW
12	Old Portsmouth Froggit (OPF)	-1.1042	50.7904	5	WOW
13	Ratton Manor Weather (RMW)	0.2501	50.794	5	WOW
14	Sidley Weather (SDW)	0.4654	50.8594	5	WOW
15	Dover Town (DVT)	1.3064	51.1335	5	WOW
16	East Studdal (ESD)	1.3324	51.20	5	WOW

Table 2

Information on the tide gauge stations used in this research for the analysis of the October–November 2023 storms. These stations are shown in Fig. 1.

No.	Tide gauge station	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Sampling interval (min)
1	St Mary's	-6.3172	49.9179	15
2	Newlyn	-5.5427	50.103	15
3	Plymouth	-4.19	50.37	15
4	Exmouth Marina	-3.4236	50.6174	0.167
5	Jersey	-2.12	49.18	15
6	Dielette	-1.86	49.55	1
7	Cherbourg	-1.63	49.65	1
8	Weymouth	-2.45	50.61	15
9	Swanage Pier	-1.9492	50.6093	0.167
10	Bournemouth	-1.87	50.71	15
11	Sandown Pier	-1.1532	50.6511	0.167
12	Portsmouth	-1.11	50.8	15
13	Newhaven	0.06	50.78	15
14	Hastings Pier	0.5729	50.8509	0.167
15	Dover	1.32	51.11	15
16	Deal Pier	1.4093	51.2238	0.167

atmospheric and oceanic data analysis, and field surveys. As the secondary objective, this study aims at inspiring further similar systematic analyses of the impacts of the UK storms on the coast.

Here, the generation and propagation of the October–November 2023 storms are first investigated using both reanalysis and measured

Table 3

Information on the wave buoy stations used in this research for the analysis of the October–November 2023 UK storms. These locations are shown in Fig. 1.

No.	Wave buoy station	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Sampling interval (s)
1	Chesil Beach	-2.522	50.602	0.78
2	West Bay	-2.751	50.694	0.78

atmospheric data. Subsequently, the generated storm surges are calculated and analysed along the English Channel. Waves' data are studied at selected locations along the south coast of the UK. In the following section, results of field surveys are presented and are reproduced using empirical runup models. Next, a meteotsunami recorded at certain coastal stretches is identified and analysed using tide gauge data. Finally, a numerical model for the generation of the storm surge and its propagation is developed. The study offers a systemic and holistic analysis of the impacts of a series of successive storms on the UK coasts.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Atmospheric and oceanic data and their analysis

Various types of data are analysed in this research namely tide gauge records, air pressure data, wind velocity, wave buoy data, and field survey data. Table 1 lists the 16 atmospheric stations analysed in this study, while Table 2 gives the 16 tide gauge stations (14 from UK, and 2 from France). Atmospheric records (air pressure, wind speed and direction) have a sampling interval of 5 min except for one record (i.e., Scilly St Mary's) which comes with a sampling interval of 60 min (Table 1). They are provided by the UK Met Office's Weather Observations Website (WOW: <https://wow.metoffice.gov.uk/>) and Wunderground weather data website (<https://www.wunderground.com/>). Spurious values were removed from the measured air pressure and wind series by an automatic quality control algorithm, which included discarding all values outside of the expected range, i.e., 940–1060 hPa for air pressure, and 0–200 km/h for wind speed, and by visual inspection. Occasional missing values were interpolated to 5-min step using linear interpolation. For better visual comparison with sea level time series, wind time series were additionally low-pass filtered using 60 min Kaiser-Bessel window (Thomson and Emery, 2024). Nonetheless, the maximum wind speeds and wind gusts, that are reported in this article, are based on the maxima of non-filtered series. We report the non-filtered values to account for high temporal and spatial variability of wind speed and gusts at different locations, but do not use them for estimating wider area sea level response or for numerical modelling. ERA5 reanalysis hourly data (Hersbach et al., 2020; Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2017), consisting of 10-m wind and mean sea level pressure (MSLP) fields, were used to extract the characteristics and tracks of the three Atlantic storms, and to describe large-scale atmospheric forcings of the observed storm surges. In addition, the ERA5 hourly values of MSLP and 10-m wind over the North Atlantic were downloaded for the period from 1940 to December 2022. The annual minimum values of MSLP and the annual maximum values of 10-m wind were extracted for each year, resulting in a set of 83 lowest annual MSLP values, and a set of 83 highest annual 10-m wind speeds at each point in our domain. The strength of the November 2023 Atlantic storms, particularly Ciarán, was ranked against these datasets.

The 16 tide gauge data have four different sampling rates of 15 min, 1 min and 0.167 min (=10 s) (Table 2), and are provided by the Inter-governmental Oceanographic Commission's (IOC) sea level monitoring facility (<https://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/>), UK tide gauge network (<https://ntslf.org/data/uk-network-real-time>) as well as UK Channel Coastal Observatory (CCO: <https://coastalmonitoring.org/>). We used wave data at two wave buoys in West Bay and Chesil Beach with sampling intervals of 0.78 s (Table 3) provided by CCO and UK's

Fig. 2. a) Part one of the tide gauge records showing original records (black), and tidal signals in each station (pink). b) The corresponding surge signals (shaded faces) for each station.

Southwest Regional Coastal Monitoring Programme (<https://www.coastalmonitoring.org/southwest/>).

For detecting storm surges (Figs. 2 and 3), we first removed tidal signals from the tide gauge records and subsequently applied a 45-min moving average filter on the data. Our tidal analysis was conducted by employing the TIDALFIT package of Grinsted (2024) which is based on ordinary least squares or robust fitting techniques to fit tidal components to the observation data. This package has been widely used for research on storms and tsunamis (e.g., Heidarzadeh et al., 2018, 2020, 2021, 2024). Two types of spectral analyses were performed in this study: Fourier and Wavelet analyses. Fourier analysis was performed applying an updated version of the Welch's (1967) power spectral density estimate developed by MathWorks (2024) via the function *pwelch* in MATLAB package (Wang et al., 2022, 2023). Hanning windows and 50 % overlaps were considered for Fourier analysis. The Wavelet package of Torrence and Compo (1998) was used for Wavelet analysis considering Morlet mother function.

2.2. Field surveys

For field surveys, we visited three locations along the south coast of the UK (Fig. 1) on 5th November 2023 to record the damage made by these storms. During the surveys, wave runup were measured based on the debris marks using a laser rangefinder of model TruPulse 200 (<https://www.lasertech.com/TruPulse-200-Rangefinder.aspx>). Runup heights were measured based on the current sea level on the day of the survey and were later corrected based on the sea level at the time of the peak of the storm (Heidarzadeh et al., 2018, 2021, 2024). Survey locations were photographed, georeferenced, and damage details were noted.

2.3. Numerical modelling

A storm surge hindcast was conducted from 00:00 UTC on 19th October to 23:00 UTC on 10th November 2023, covering the duration of the three storms, using the Coupled-Ocean-Atmosphere-Wave-Sediment

Fig. 3. a) Part two of the tide gauge records showing original records (black), and tidal signals in each station (pink). b) The corresponding surge signals (shaded faces) for each station.

Transport (COAWST) Modelling System (Warner et al., 2010). The COAWST system employs ROMS (Shchepetkin and McWilliams, 2005) as the ocean model, and ERA5 fields for atmospheric forcing. Additionally, it has the capability to integrate the third-generation spectral wave model SWAN (Booij et al., 1999) into ROMS. By integrating these models, the hindcast could consider the effects of waves on storm surges (e.g., wave-current interactions). During the simulation which included waves, ROMS and SWAN exchanged simulated results, such as sea levels and significant wave heights, every 10 min. The bathymetries in both models were from GEBCO-2022 bathymetric database, which has an original grid resolution of 15 arc-sec (Weatherall et al., 2015). The outermost domain (D1) covered large parts of the Atlantic Ocean, and two sub-domains (D2 and D3) were subsequently nested into the English channel (Fig. 4). Following experiences from previous studies (e.g., Heidarzadeh et al., 2023), the spatial resolution of the innermost grid (D3) was set at 1 km to examine the fundamental characteristics of storm surges across the entire English Channel. In ROMS, the computational grids were vertically divided into 10 layers to accurately model three-dimensional structures and sea bottom stress (Weisberg and

Zheng, 2008). The other configurations and information of the nested grid system are summarized in Table 4.

To assess the impacts of wind stress, air pressure, wave, and astronomical tide on storm surges, six simulations were performed under different forcing scenarios: with wind stress and air pressure (S + P), only wind stress (S), only air pressure (P), wind stress, air pressure, and wave (S + P + W), only astronomical tides (T), and wind stress, air pressure, and astronomical tides (S + P + T). The first three simulations aimed to examine the basic mechanism of the storm surges, while the last three focused on the potential impacts of waves and astronomical tides on storm surges in the English Channel. The case T was only used to subtract the astronomical tide from the result in the case S + P + T. In these simulations, the 10-m wind and mean sea level pressure fields in ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020) were employed as the meteorological forcings, and TPX09-atlas (Egbert and Erofeeva, 2002) was used to impose astronomical tides on the lateral boundaries of ROMS. Also, the 10-m wind speed was converted to the wind stress, with the wind speed thresholds of 8 m/s and 30 m/s used for calculating the surface drag coefficient C_D using the following equation (Powell et al., 2003;

Fig. 4. The nested grid system comprising of three interconnected grid domains (D1, D2, and D3) to model October–November 2023 storm chain.

Table 4

The details of the computational domains, grid sizes and spacing, and the domain-dependent settings of the nested grid system used for modelling storm surges and waves. Note that 3D and 2D time steps in ROMS are separately shown.

Grid name	Spatial coverage (degree)	Grid spacing (m)	Time steps (s)		Horizontal viscosity coefficient (m ² /s)
			ROMS (3D / 2D)	SWAN	
D1	Lon: -58.86° W-19.86°W Lat: 20.18° N-69.93°N	25,000	60 / 6	300	100
D2	Lon: -8.60° W-2.88°W Lat: 41.88° N-53.92°N	5000	20 / 2	120	50
D3	Lon: -4.00° W-1.97°W Lat: 48.30° N-51.19°N	1000	4 / 0.4	60	30

Heidarzadeh et al., 2023; Iwamoto et al., 2023).

$$C_D = \begin{cases} (1 - 1.89 \times V \times 10^{-2}) \times 1.28 \times 10^{-3} & V < 8 \\ (1 + 1.078 \times V \times 10^{-1}) \times 5.81 \times 10^{-4} & 8 \leq V < 30 \\ 2.46 \times 10^{-3} & 30 \leq V \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Of note, constant values of seawater temperature and salinity (i.e., 26.5 °C and 34.5 PSU) were used in our simulations. Baroclinic effects on the storm surges were excluded. Moreover, simulating relatively high-frequency changes in sea level related to waves (e.g., infragravity waves) was beyond the scope of this study.

3. Generation and propagation of the storms

The recorded air pressure time series show the pressure drops on 27–30 October, 2–3 November (Storm Ciarán) and 4–5 November (Storm Domingos) (Fig. 5). All three pressure drops coincided with strong onshore winds (blowing towards the south coast of the UK) (Fig. 6). The first pressure drop (27–30 October) was the shallowest and longest one among the three pressure drops (Fig. 5). It was associated with the outer isobars of an unnamed storm that held a rather steady position some 200–600 km west of the Irish coast for a 4-day period of

27–30 October. At this time, the minimum central MSLP dropped to 974 hPa, and winds reached speeds of up to 18 km/h over the open ocean and up to 14 km/h on the European Atlantic coasts, including the south coast of the UK (ERA5 data, not shown). As this was a relatively stationary storm, it resulted in sustained southwesterly winds blowing towards the south coast of the UK for 4 days (Fig. 6). The continued presence of a low-pressure system over the UK and the sustained onshore winds, led to an overall rise in sea level along the English Channel, with the highest residual sea level recorded at Bournemouth (68.2 cm) (Figs. 5 and 6). When Ciarán struck a few days later, the new storm surge started from an already elevated sea level.

Storm Ciarán hit the UK with full force on 2nd November 2023. According to our data, the measured coastal air pressure values dropped as low as 947.9 hPa (WFN), and the measured wind speeds reached 99.8 km/h with wind gusts of up to 149.6 km/h (JER) (Table 5). The storm began as a closed low-pressure system that formed in the western Atlantic off the coast of Nova Scotia (Canada) on 30–31 October 2023 (ERA5 data, not shown). From there, Ciarán spread east-northeast across the Atlantic and towards the coast of the UK, deepening and gaining strength along its path. The storm was at its strongest from the midday hours of 1st November until the early morning hours of 2nd November. During this time, MSLP of the storm’s centre dropped to 954 hPa, and winds reached up to 31 km/h (ERA5 data, Fig. 7). Ciarán made landfall on the south coast of the UK, approximately at the time of its greatest strength. Fig. 7 shows snapshots of the ERA5 MSLP and wind speed at 10-m height at 00:00 and 06:00 UTC of 2nd November, i.e., at the time of landfall. At these times, both low air pressure and strong onshore winds combined to raise the sea level over the English Channel producing storm surges (Fig. 6).

Much like Ciarán, Storm Domingos developed as a relatively shallow closed low-pressure system (MSLP of 1005 hPa) in the western Atlantic Ocean (ERA5 data; not shown). The system first appeared off the coast of the northern US in the early morning hours of 1st November, from where it propagated northeastward, deepening to ~980 hPa over the next ~36 h. Then, from the evening hours of 2nd November, it took a more eastward track, crossing the Atlantic Ocean within the next 36 h. Domingos deepened and strengthened as it propagated, with the central MSLP dropping to 960 hPa and wind speeds increasing to 30 km/h approximately 12 h before landfall (ERA5 data). As it moved further eastward across the Atlantic, Domingos widened, and the associated spatial pressure gradients decreased. Consequently, winds were weaker at the time of landfall (midday 4th November), with ERA5 speeds of up to 25 km/h over the Atlantic, and up to 15 km/h over the Spanish and

Fig. 5. a) Air pressure records and b) residual sea level (storm surge) for each station. Minimum values of mean sea level air pressure (surface air pressure at some stations) are denoted for both Ciarán and Domingos in a), and maximum surge heights related to both storms in b). Shaded faces indicate storms in a) and surge signals in b). Dashed blue lines denote approximate arrival times of Ciarán and Domingos centres to each station.

French Atlantic coasts, where coastal winds were strongest (Figs. 6 and 7). The latter explains why this storm caused more damage in France and Spain than on the south coast of the UK. Along the English Channel, minimum MSLP of 958.4 hPa was measured in WFN (in Weymouth), and maximum winds (51.5 km/h) and wind gusts (82.1 km/h) again in Jersey (Table 5).

Characteristics of storm surges generated by Ciarán and Domingos are extracted from tide gauge data and are shown in Figs. 2, 3, 5 and 6 and listed in Table 5. These three consecutive storms generated one of the longest-duration storm surges recorded in the region as their combined durations ranged from 4.9 days (Deal Pier) to 12.6 days (Weymouth). The average storm surge duration was 10.5 days (Table 5) based on the data from 13 tide gauge stations. The amplitude of storm surges generated by Ciarán was in the range from 53 cm (Deal Pier) to 167 cm (Jersey) with an average value of 92 cm.

Notably, Jersey, which recorded the highest surge during Ciarán, was one of the hardest hit locations and suffered severe damage (Met Office, 2023). For Domingos, storm surge amplitudes were in the range of 55–95 cm with an average amplitude of 74 cm (Table 5). The highest surge amplitude of 95 cm occurred in Dielette (French coast of the English Channel). Based on the data presented in Table 5, it can be concluded that the storm surge generated by Ciarán was approximately 22 % higher than that from Domingos.

It should also be noted that three storm systems generated distinctly different types of storm surges (Figs. 2, 3 and 5b). The first storm

resulted with prolonged 4–5 day sea level rise without a clear maximum. Ciarán produced a single, short-lasting (~12 h) surge peak whose rise was supported by both low MSLP and strong onshore winds and whose rapid decline coincided with a change in wind direction (Fig. 6). Domingos resulted with a ~48-h sea level increase characterized by a single peak at some stations and multiple peaks at others.

4. Field surveys

The purposes of conducting field surveys were to record wave runup and document the damage made by the storms on coastal areas. Such damage and runup databases are critically helpful for developing coastal storm mitigation strategies (e.g., Tamura et al., 2021; Takagi and Heidarzadeh, 2023). Additionally, field observations help to understand and explain the results of numerical and analytical studies, such as those conducted in this research, and provide data for improving storm models (e.g., Muhari et al., 2019; Heidarzadeh et al., 2024). Although such databases have been developed for various parts of the world such as USA (e.g., Fritz et al., 2007, 2008) and Japan (e.g., Le et al., 2019; Takabatake et al., 2018), very few research are available on runup surveys of UK storms (e.g., Spencer et al., 2015), which has motivated us to conduct the field surveys following the October–November 2023 storm chain.

Results of field surveys of the storms in Chesil Beach, West Bay, and Sidmouth are presented in Figs. 8–10, respectively. The surveyed runup

Fig. 6. Surge signal, low-pass filtered air pressure records and low-pass filtered wind records at five stations, from top to bottom: Newlyn, Dielette, Bournemouth, Newhaven and Hastings.

heights are 4.1 m (Chesil Beach), and 2.1 m (West Bay) (Table 6). No runup height could be measured in Sidmouth as the beach was protected by a vertical seawall and a clear watermark or debris mark was not visible on the seawall. It is noted that as Ciarán was the largest storm among the three storms, the surveyed runup heights can be mainly attributed to Ciarán.

Chesil Beach is among the most endangered coasts in the UK when it comes to storm surge and ocean waves—this is because the beach is open to the southwest, with a fetch extending far to the Atlantic Ocean (West, 2014). Many historical floods have thus occurred here, with the first records of floods dating back to the sixth century (West, 2014). Nowadays, Chesil Beach is one of the most defended coasts in the UK and is designed to withstand the largest storms as a populated community resides behind the beach at a low elevation. A variety of coastal defence systems are installed here including a natural pebble dyke, a concrete sea wall, rock armour, gabion baskets and concreted rock armour (Fig. 8). At the time of the survey (5th November 2023 at around noon), the weather was partly sunny and stable, as all three storm systems had dissipated. However, the sea remained turbulent, with large waves and swells still present. A clear debris line was observed along the Chesil

Beach enabling a runup measurement of 4.1 m at this location (Fig. 8, Table 6). Minimal damage was observed here, including the accumulation of tree branches and debris along the coast, as well as the displacement of beach shingle and pebbles onto pedestrian pathways (Fig. 8).

West Bay is protected by a 5-m tall shingle dune with a rock armour core (which is not visible). This location is a major tourist attraction in the UK because of its scenery Jurassic coast and cliffs (Fig. 9). The area was less impacted by the storms compared to Chesil Beach. With the aid of clear debris mark along the coast, we measured a runup height of 2.1 m here (Fig. 9). The surveyed runup here is around half of that in Chesil Beach (Table 6). The damage in West Bay was minimal, mostly consisting of the displacement of beach shingle onto nearby roads. A fresh landslide was observed at the toe of the cliff which was most likely triggered by the November 2023 storms (Fig. 9).

Sidmouth is mainly protected by a vertical seawall along with a shingle berm in front of it which acts as a scour protection for the seawall foundation (Fig. 10). Similar to other two locations, the coast sustained minimal damage here, mostly consisting of displacement of shingle onto the coastal roads. As there were no watermarks or debris marks present,

Table 5

Characteristics of storm surges, air pressure drops and wind speeds generated by the 2023 Storms Ciarán and Domingos at stations along the coasts of the English Channel. NA represent "Not Applicable". Atmospheric data was measured at the WOW/wunderground meteorological station closest to tide gauge (Fig. 1).

No	Tide gauge station	Ciarán maximum surge amplitude (cm)	Domingos maximum surge amplitude (cm)	Total Surge duration (day)	Meteo. Station	Ciarán Pressure drop (hPa)	Domingos pressure drop (hPa)	Maximum wind speed (km/h)	Maximum wind gust (km/h)
1	St Mary's	57 ± 10	55 ± 10	7.4	SSM	36.0	28	85.4	123.9
2	Newlyn	78 ± 10	70 ± 10	11.9	SLV	38.8	26.2	46.7	78.9
3	Plymouth	80 ± 10	79 ± 10	12.2	SAL	31.6	24.8	28.8	51.5
4	Exmouth Marina	72 ± 10	71 ± 10	8.2	WCW	41.3	24	25.6	43.9
5	Jersey	167 ± 10	N/A	NA	JER	39.4	24.5	99.8	149.6
6	Dielette	151 ± 10	95 ± 10	12.3	SRV	42.3	23.3	70.6	70.6
7	Cherbourg	85 ± 10	77 ± 10	12.3	BNO	42.7	23.3	40.3	55.4
8	Weymouth	91 ± 10	73 ± 10	12.6	WFN	43.7	22.8	40.0	49.6
9	Swanage Pier	76 ± 10	68 ± 10	10.0	WRW	44.0	22.3	35.6	69.1
10	Bournemouth	> 68 ± 10	> 38 ± 10	NA	BH6	44.3	22.3	38.2	67.0
11	Sandown Pier	> 48 ± 10	85 ± 10	NA	NCR	45.5	21.9	41.0	62.6
12	Portsmouth	96 ± 10	76 ± 10	12.1	OPF	45.3	22.0	40.4	51.5
13	Newhaven	95 ± 10	91 ± 10	12.3	RMW	44.9	20.7	35.4	62.8
14	Hastings Pier	97 ± 10	66 ± 10	10.0	SDW	44.7	20.6	17.8	53.3
15	Dover	84 ± 10	64 ± 10	10.4	DVT	43.5	19.2	27.4	36.3
16	Deal Pier	53 ± 10	61 ± 10	4.9	ESD	44.2	19.1	38.2	58.7
Average		92 ± 10	74 ± 10	10.5		42.0	22.8	44.5	67.8

a runup height could not be measured in Sidmouth.

5. Wave characteristics, and wave runup

This section is aimed at reproducing the observed runup heights using existing empirical runup models. For hazard prediction and planning mitigation against wave runup and overtopping, it is essential to forecast runup heights based on the storm and wave characteristics as well as beach features such as slope angle, and type of the beach materials. Wave runup is normally represented by $R_{2\%}$ which implies runup exceeded by 2 % of wave runup events.

Several equations have been proposed in the literature for predicting wave runup ($R_{2\%}$) that use various input parameters. Here, we model the observed runup in Chesil Beach and West Bay using three empirical runup models. For simplicity, it is assumed that both locations have similar beach materials (gravel). While this may have a slight impact on the results, it is expected to be negligible. We also overlook the impact of wave setup as it is usually trivial as compared to wave runup. Vousdoukas et al. (2012) proposed the following equation for wave runup:

$$R_{2\%} = 0.53 \tan(\beta) \sqrt{H_s L_0} + 0.58 \frac{\tan(\beta)}{\sqrt{H_s/L_0}} \sqrt{H_s^3/L_0} + 0.45 \quad (2)$$

where $R_{2\%}$ is the runup exceeded by 2 % of wave runup events, H_s is deepwater significant wave height, L_0 is deepwater wavelength, and β is beach slope. Another model was proposed by Poate et al. (2016) which has the following form:

$$R_{2\%} = C (\tan\beta)^{0.5} T_p H_s \quad (3)$$

where T_p is peak wave period, and C is a coefficient ($C = 0.33$). Other parameters in this equation were introduced earlier. According to Ruggiero et al. (2001), wave runup can be calculated using the following equation:

$$R_{2\%} = 0.27 (H_s L_0 \tan\beta)^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

where all parameters in this equation were introduced earlier. To calculate the peak wave period (T_p) and offshore significant wave height (H_s), we plotted a 3-h segment of the storm waves based on offshore wave buoys in Chesil Beach and West Bay (Fig. 11). For deepwater wavelength (L_0) calculations, small-amplitude wave theory was applied (Sorensen, 2006), as follows:

$$L_0 = \frac{g T_p^2}{2\pi} \tanh\left(\frac{2\pi}{L_0} d\right) \quad (5)$$

where d is water depth at the location of offshore wave buoys, and g is gravitational acceleration. Other parameters are defined earlier. Water depth (d) at the location of Chesil Beach and West Bay wave buoys are 12 m and 10 m, respectively.

The results of comparison between observed and modelled runup are presented in Table 7. The following equation was applied to calculate the difference (ϵ) between observations (R_o) and modelled runup ($R_{2\%}$) values:

$$\epsilon = \frac{|R_{2\%} - R_o|}{R_o} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where $R_{2\%}$ is modelled runup, and R_o is observed runup. The mathematical symbol $|x|$ represent the absolute value of x .

Wave characteristics (dominant periods and amplitudes) are presented in Fig. 11 which reveals that wave dominant periods were 14.4 s in Chesil Beach and 15.3 s in West Bay (see spectra in Fig. 11). Based on wavelet analysis, the wave spectra at both Chesil Beach and West Bay exhibit characteristics of a unimodal wave spectrum, with wave energy primarily dominated by swell. Other data required to apply the three empirical equations are given in Table 7. According to the results presented in Table 7, Eqs. (2) and (4) can reproduce the observed runup heights with an error margin of 8–25 % which seems reasonable. However, Eq. (3) gives high mismatch values of 156–318 % implying significant overestimation of the observations. Therefore, Eq. (3) does not seem suitable for runup prediction, at least for the two locations examined in this study, i.e., Chesil Beach and West Bay. It is noteworthy that Eqs. (2) and (4) produce closely aligned results, indicating that the observed runup can be consistently and sustainably replicated by at least two independent empirical models.

In summary, this exercise reveals that runup empirical equations presented in Eqs. (2) and (4) can be successfully applied to predict potential runup heights of storms along the south coast of the UK. As we tested the performance of Eqs. (2) and (4) at two coastal locations, it is recommended to further examine their performances in other locations along the south coast of the UK.

6. Meteotsunami

Meteotsunamis, also known as meteorological tsunamis, are

Fig. 7. Synoptic situation during Storms Ciarán and Domingos. Plots depict MSLP and wind velocities. Wind speeds higher than 15 m/s are coloured. Low-pressure centre of the storm is marked with "X" in each plot. Situations are given at: (a) 2nd November 2023, 12:00 UTC, (b) 2nd November 2023, 06:00 UTC, (c) 4th November 2023, 06:00 UTC, (d) 4th November 2023, 12:00 UTC, that is at times at which surges related to storms Ciarán (a and b) and Domingos (c and d) were the highest.

Fig. 8. Results of field surveys in Chesil Beach (Portland) showing various types of coastal defence, storm damage, and runup. Height of 7–14 m for the natural pebble dyke is based on [Bennett et al. \(2009\)](#). This survey was conducted on 5th November 2023.

tsunami-like waves that are produced by smaller-scale atmospheric disturbances (~ 10 – 100 km in size) ([Monserrat et al., 2006](#); [Šepić et al., 2015](#); [Heidarzadeh and Rabinovich, 2021](#)). According to [Proudman \(1929\)](#), exceptional long ocean waves (later termed as meteotsunamis by [Monserrat et al., 2006](#)) occur when the speed of an atmospheric disturbance (U) approaches the speed of long oceanic waves ($C = \sqrt{gd}$, where g is gravitational acceleration and d is ocean water depth). In other words, the necessary factor for meteotsunamis occurrence is: $F_r = U/C \approx 1$, where F_r is Froude number ([Šepić et al., 2015](#)). Therefore, a combination of factors should be met for a meteotsunami to be generated.

Occasionally storms produce meteotsunamis ([Heidarzadeh and Rabinovich, 2021](#); [Medvedev et al., 2022](#)), although not at every instance and at every coastal location, as not all storms have embedded shorter periods atmospheric pressure disturbances capable of generating meteotsunamis. However, storm-generated meteotsunamis are usually hidden within the intensive wave and surge oscillations. To reveal them, band-pass filters are normally applied to storm sea level and air pressure records.

For the case of the October–November 2023 UK storm chain, we were able to detect meteotsunamis at four locations as shown in [Fig. 12](#). It is noted that our meteotsunami analysis was not exhaustive and it was not aimed at discovering all meteotsunami incidents during the October–November 2023 storm chain. For this analysis, a band-pass filter with a period band of 5–90 min was applied to the storm sea level waveforms ([Fig. 12](#)). For the part of data scrutinised in [Fig. 12](#), we can identify clear meteotsunami at four stations (Dielette, Cherbourg, Swanage Pier, and Hastings Pier). However, two stations (Exmouth

Marina and Deal Pier) do not show any meteotsunami which could be attributed to the specific bathymetric features or coastline geometries at these locations. The characteristics of the detected meteotsunamis are listed in [Table 8](#), showing a maximum wave amplitude of 17–23 cm and a wave period of 11–40 min. By comparing the amplitudes of the meteotsunami to those of wave runup and surges ([Tables 5 and 6](#)), it might appear that meteotsunamis were weaker than wave runup and surges. However, it is noteworthy that meteotsunamis are classified as extremely long waves due to their long periods of 11–40 min ([Table 8](#)) and thus can cause large damage despite their small amplitudes as long-period waves can cause extensive inundations, and strong and damaging currents, even when they have low amplitudes (e.g., [Linares et al., 2019](#)).

Regarding the generation mechanism of the meteotsunami, since the mean depth of the English Channel is ~ 50 m, the strongest meteotsunamis are expected for atmospheric disturbances travelling over the channel at a speed of approximately 22 m/s (i.e., $C = \sqrt{9.81 \times 50} = 22.1$ m/s). From the ERA5 data, we can estimate the mean speed of storm Ciarán over the English Channel (from 22:00 UTC on 1st November to 11:00 UTC on 2nd November; [Fig. 1](#)) to be approximately 15 m/s, which is close to an optimal speed of 22 m/s. However, for a meteotsunami to develop, the atmospheric disturbance should be several times smaller than the size of the shelf, channel, or bay over which it propagates. Given that the dimensions of Storm Ciarán were comparable to those of the English Channel ([Fig. 7b](#)), it is unlikely that Ciarán directly generated meteotsunamis. However, intense smaller-scale air pressure disturbances ($O(10$ km)) capable of producing meteotsunamis are often detected along the temperature fronts of

Fig. 9. Results of field surveys in West Bay showing storm damage, coastal protection structures and wave runup. This survey was conducted on 5th November 2023.

extratropical cyclones (e.g., Rabinovich et al., 2023), which was likely the case during Ciarán. These disturbances can propagate faster than extratropical storms themselves, possibly reaching the above-estimated resonant speed of ~ 22 m/s. Unfortunately, we were unable to confirm the presence of such tsunamigenic atmospheric disturbances in atmospheric pressure data since the resolution of these data was not sufficient to detect small-scale air pressure changes.

7. Numerical modelling

7.1. Simulation results from different forcing scenarios

Fig. 13 depicts the time series of observed and simulated storm surges at 16 tide stations caused by Storms Ciarán and Domingos under three different forcing scenarios consisting of S (only wind stress), P (only air pressure), and S + P (combined wind stress and air pressure). According to model S scenario (blue lines in Fig. 13), the wind stress caused a minor decrease in sea levels at the initial stage of the storm duration along the UK coast (black-marked locations). After that, the sea level slightly increased around 00:00 UTC on 2nd November followed by a larger drop of about 20 cm to 80 cm after 6–9 h (the blue lines, Fig. 13). In contrast, along the French coast (red-marked locations), the wind stress caused an increase in sea levels, reaching a maximum of 100 cm in Diellete during Storm Ciarán. Also, the subsequent drop in sea level was more minor. Looking at the impacts of air pressure (P scenario; the orange lines in Fig. 13), it can be seen that it increased sea levels in the entire English Channel, reaching a maximum of above 50 cm. The combined scenario, i.e. S + P scenario shown by black lines in Fig. 13, confirms that ROMS can reproduce the temporal evolutions of observed

storm surges reasonably well by combining the actions of wind stress and air pressure.

Our modelling results confirm that the contribution of wind stress to surge can be either positive (i.e., resulting in an increase in sea level) or negative (i.e., resulting in a decrease in sea level). Total surge height ultimately depends on both wind stress and air pressure, with the most hazardous events occurring when air pressure significantly drops (as in hurricanes, or extratropical storms), and strong winds blow towards the shore. However, hurricanes and storms can also be associated with exceptional offshore winds which can be of such strength that they annul effect of lowered air pressure, or even cause reverse (negative) surges. A recent example is the 2022 Hurricane Ian (Florida, USA) during which both normal (i.e., positive) and reverse surges were recorded along the Florida coast, with reverse surges strictly related to offshore winds (Heidarzadeh et al., 2023). Note that periodic fluctuations in storm surges which were observed at some tide stations (e.g., Dover and Hastings Pier) were not reproduced by our numerical modelling. The authors address this subject later in the article (Section 7.2).

To illustrate the mechanism of the normal and reverse surges that were modelled for the scenario which only included wind stress forcing (scenario S), Fig. 14 depicts the spatiotemporal evolutions of sea level during Storm Ciarán under the scenario S. Initially, while the storm was positioned offshore, southeasterly to southwesterly winds dominated over the area of interest. As the storm approached the English Channel, a strong westerly wind up to 40 m/s blew at the English Channel's entrance, with a weaker southerly wind now blowing at the eastern part of the channel (Fig. 14). This caused an inflow of seawater from the offshore regions, resulting in an increase in sea level throughout the English Channel at 03:00 UTC on 2nd November. After Ciarán's centre left the area, westerly to southwesterly winds parallel to the channel

Fig. 10. Results of field surveys in Sidmouth showing storm damage, and coastal protection structures. This survey was conducted on 5th November 2023.

Table 6
Results of runup survey following the October–November 2023 UK storms.

Location	Date and time of survey	Measured runup (m)	Tidal correction (m)	Final runup (m)
Chesil Beach	5th Nov. 2023 at 11:30 PM	3.9	+0.2	4.1
West Bay*	5th Nov. 2023 at 13:00 PM	2.2	-0.1	2.1

* As there was no tide gauge in West Bay, for tidal correction, the results of two neighbouring tide gauge stations (Weymouth and Exmouth Marina) were considered.

prevailed over the sea, and the wind speed gradually decreased from 09:00 UTC on 2nd November to 03:00 UTC on 3rd November (Fig. 14). During this interval, the sea level experienced a decrease exceeding 50 cm along the UK coast, and an increase of up to 100 cm along the French coast. These results suggest likely seawater transport due to the prevailing winds, leading to the decrease in sea level along the UK coast, and the accompanied Ekman transport as a contributing factor to the storm surge along the French coast.

7.2. Contribution of waves and tides to simulations

The contributions of wave (W) and astronomical tides (T) to the storm surge simulations were assessed (Figs. 15 and 16). As shown in Fig. 15, under the coarse grid system (1 km) relative to the characteristic scales of infragravity waves, the effects of waves on storm surges seem negligible at four tide stations shown in Fig. 15; simulation including waves is almost equal to the baseline S + P simulation. However,

inclusion of tides to the model, in the case of Storm Ciarán, results in shift of phases of the peak storm surges at Dielette and Hastings Pier for several hours, more closely aligning the simulated and the observed maxima at these two stations. This phase shift possibly occurred due to changes in the propagation speeds of storm surges and astronomical tides by temporally varying water depths (i.e., tide-surge interaction) (Horsburgh and Wilson, 2007; Idier et al., 2012). Additionally, periodic fluctuations in storm surges were simulated in Dover, having nearly the same amplitude as those in the observations. Similar results can be confirmed in the case of Storm Domingos; however, the effects of the astronomical tides on storm surges were weaker, even at Dielette and Dover.

In Fig. 16, we compare the S + P simulation with S + P + W and S + P + T simulations for both storms to quantify the impacts of waves (W) and tides (T) on our surge modelling results. Fig. 16 illustrates that the contributions of waves and astronomical tides were site-specific. It also confirms that tide-surge interactions significantly increased eastward along the English Channel (Haigh et al., 2010; Idier et al., 2012). The amplification due to the astronomical tides in Storm Ciarán was several times larger than that of Storm Domingos. The reason behind this could be attributed to the spring-neap tidal cycle: the storm surges in Storm Ciarán occurred close to the peak of the spring tide, while those by Storm Domingos occurred when the astronomical tides shifted to the neap tide (see Figs. 2 and 3). This mechanism is further discussed and modelled in the next section.

Increase in maximum surge height is much smaller for model which includes waves (S + P + W) (Fig. 15, bottom panels) than for model which includes tides (S + P + T) (Fig. 15, upper panel), with the wave effect mostly restricted to the southern stretches of the channel. To reproduce the recorded sea level height of 167 cm in Jersey (Table 5), it

Fig. 11. Characteristics of waves recorded on Chesil Beach and West Bay wave buoys during the November 2023 Storm Ciarán consisting of waveforms (the first and second rows), spectra (third row) and wavelet (fourth row). The colour bar’s unit for wavelet plots is $\log_2(E)$ where E is wave energy.

Table 7

Observed and modelled wave runup heights at Chesil Beach and West Bay resulting from the October–November 2023 storm chain.

Location	Runup equation ^a	Beach slope ($\tan\beta$) ^b	T_p (s)	H_s (m)	L_0 (m) ^c	Modelled runup, $R_{2\%}$	Observed runup, R_o	ϵ (%) ^d
Chesil Beach	Eq. (2)	0.15	14.4	5.7	150.1	3.3	4.1	20
	Eq. (3)	0.15	14.4	5.7	150.1	10.5	4.1	156
	Eq. (4)	0.15	14.4	5.7	150.1	3.1	4.1	25
West Bay	Eq. (2)	0.10	15.3	5.5	147.2	2.3	2.1	8
	Eq. (3)	0.10	15.3	5.5	147.2	8.8	2.1	318
	Eq. (4)	0.10	15.3	5.5	147.2	2.4	2.1	16

^a Eq. (2) is proposed by Vousdoukas et al. (2012), Eq. (3) is developed by Poate et al. (2016) and Eq. (4) is from Ruggiero et al. (2001).

^b Beach slopes are based on Carr (1983) for the Chesil Beach. For West Bay, the slope was approximated during the field survey.

^c For wavelength calculations, the small-amplitude wave theory is applied. Water depth (d) at the location of Chesil Beach and West Bay wave buoys are 12 m and 10 m, respectively.

^d ϵ is calculated based on Eq. (6).

appears necessary to include both waves and tides in the model. The S + P model captures an amplitude of 110 cm (Fig. 13), while Fig. 16 highlights the potential contributions of tides and waves to the maximum storm surges: approximately 40 cm and 10 cm, respectively. The impact of waves on storm surges may vary locally when finer grids (on the order of 10 m) are used to resolve wave-breaking zones.

Although this spatial scale falls beyond the scope of our modelling, a more site-specific approach could provide additional insights into storm surges in Jersey.

Fig. 12. The meteotsunami components generated by the November 2023 Storm Ciarán. The waveforms presented here are band-pass filtered for signals in the period domain from 5 min to 90 min. Note that only four stations show meteotsunamis, as indicated.

Table 8
Characteristics of meteotsunamis recorded during November 2023 Storm Ciarán at four locations across the English Channel.

No	Tide gauge station	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Maximum meteotsunami amplitude (cm)	Meteotsunami period (min) ^a
1	Dielette	-1.86	49.55	23	30–40
2	Cherbourg	-1.63	49.65	18	30
3	Swanage Pier	-1.9492	50.6093	17	11–16
4	Hastings Pier	0.5729	50.8509	22	20–35

^a Here, wave periods are calculated based on visual inspection of the waveforms as the waves are clearly visible.

7.3. Momentum budget analysis

To assess the impacts of spring-neap tidal cycles on storm surges, we performed the depth-averaged momentum budget analysis at the

eastern English Channel. The momentum balance in the Cartesian coordinates can be written as follows (Weisberg and Zheng, 2006):

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial t} + \underbrace{(\bar{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \nabla) \bar{\mathbf{u}}}_{ADV} + \underbrace{\mathbf{f} \times \bar{\mathbf{u}}}_{COR} = \frac{-1}{\rho_w} \nabla p + \underbrace{\frac{\tau_s}{\rho_w D}}_{SSTR} + \underbrace{\frac{-\tau_b}{\rho_w D}}_{BSTR} + \underbrace{\nu \nabla^2 \bar{\mathbf{u}}}_{VISC} \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ is depth-averaged velocity (m/s), \mathbf{f} is Coriolis parameter (1/s), p is pressure (Pa), D is total depth (m), τ_s is surface stress (Pa), τ_b is bottom stress (Pa), and ν is kinematic viscosity (m²/s). Here the abbreviated terms in Eq. (7) are: ACC (local acceleration), ADV (horizontal advection), COR (Coriolis), PG (pressure gradient), SSTR (surface stress), BSTR (bottom stress), and VISC (horizontal viscosity). The bold style letters in Eq. (7) represent vectors, and sea water density ρ_w (kg/m³) is considered constant. Note that the bottom stress with quadratic parametrization was used in this study; i.e., $\tau_b = \rho_w C_b |\bar{\mathbf{u}}| \bar{\mathbf{u}}$, where $C_b = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$.

The effects of the astronomical tides on storm surges were evaluated using Eq. (7) and the results from the cases S + P, T, and S + P + T are compared. We know that the nonlinear effects of the tide-surge

Fig. 13. a) Simulated waveforms for three forcing scenarios for the November 2023 Storms Ciarán and Domingos. The scenarios are: (i) using both wind stress (S) and air pressure (P) as forcing marked by black waveforms as “S + P”; (ii) using only wind stress (S) as forcing marked by blue waveforms as “S”; and (iii) using only air pressure (P) as forcing marked by orange waveforms as “P”. Here, observations are shown by grey dots. b) Locations of 16 tide gauge stations.

Fig. 14. Snapshots of storm surge simulations for the November 2023 Storms Ciarán and Domingos using only wind stress (scenario S) as the external forcing. The location of the central position of Storm Ciarán based on ERA5 is also shown (the blue line). The vectors represent the wind fields based on ERA5.

Fig. 15. Sensitivity of the simulations of the November 2023 Storms Ciarán and Domingos to various scenarios comprising: the forcing scenario S + P (black waveforms), adding the effects of wave (S + P + W) (green waveforms), and simultaneous simulation of storm surges and the astronomical tides (S + P + T) (orange waveforms). Here, observations are shown by grey dots.

interactions (Idier et al., 2012) impact the momentums: the spatiotemporal changes in tidal currents can affect ADV, ACC, COR, BSTR, and VISC, while those of the total depth can affect SSTR and BSTR.

Fig. 17 shows the time series of the momentum changes by tides at the eastern English Channel during storms Ciarán and Domingos. We should note that these were the spatial averages at locations where the maximum storm surge increased by tides over 20 cm in the eastern English Channel (see Fig. 16). It is evident that the amplitudes of differences in Storm Ciarán are about four times larger than those in Storm Domingos. Prior to Storm Ciarán’s approach, ACC, ADV, and PG had a similar amplitude (Fig. 17). ADV and PG prevailed when the storm was near Dover (around 09:00 UTC on 2nd November). As expected, the amplitudes of SSTR and BSTR also increased around this time but were still smaller than that of ADV. The balances of the momentum changes (the bottom panels in Fig. 17) further support this finding. These results indicate that the possible reason for amplifying storm surges by spring tide was the strong tidal currents (the term ADV), with limited impacts from water depth changes (the terms SSTR and BSTR).

8. Discussions

8.1. Power of storm Ciarán as compared to UK storms in 1940–2022

Haigh et al. (2016) noted that most of the wide-area extreme sea level events (events where extreme sea levels are observed along long stretches of coastline) occur along the southern coast of the UK as storms propagate eastward across the UK, with their centre passing more than

300 km north of the English Channel. In comparison to these storms, the centre of Ciarán moved directly along the English Channel across the south coast of the UK, thus setting the stage for an exceptional surge. Furthermore, Ciarán not only tracked directly over the channel, but was also characterised by the lowest MSLP ever recorded over England and Wales. The exceptional nature of this storm is further highlighted in Fig. 18, which compares the ERA5-reproduced MSLP and 10-m winds during Ciarán with the lowest annual ERA5 MSLP and 10-m winds recorded between 1940 and 2022. Over almost the entire English Channel, the Ciarán MSLP values were the third lowest and wind speed values were the third and the second highest of the entire period.

8.2. Contribution to storm hazard prediction and mitigation

Key factors in storm hazard prediction and mitigation include storm surge heights, storm runoff on coastal structures and beaches, and storm overtopping rates. These factors significantly influence the extent of damage to coastal areas and determine the limits of inundation. Our study provides critical data on these parameters for one of the largest storm events in the UK. This information can be used to assess the adequacy of existing coastal defenses, particularly in scenarios where a future storm similar to Ciarán coincides with high tide levels. In addition, the validated storm surge model developed in this study offers a valuable tool for coastal authorities and researchers. It can be applied to scenario-based studies to simulate potential storm surge events and to develop detailed inundation maps for the south coast of the UK. Furthermore, the model can be used to investigate the impacts of climate

Fig. 16. The changes in the maximum storm surges during the two storms by contributing waves (W) and astronomical tides (T) relative to the S + P simulation.

change on storm surge heights, providing critical insights for long-term coastal resilience planning and adaptive management strategies.

8.3. Increased hazards from successive storms

An important feature of the October–November 2023 storm chain was the successive nature of three storms generated in the period from 27th October to 5th November (i.e., an unnamed storm, Ciarán and Domingos), which complicated recovery efforts. Our analysis revealed that Storm Ciarán arrived when the sea level was already elevated due to the effects of the preceding unnamed storm, which intensified the height of the storm surges. Similar successive storms occurred in January–February 2014 (six storms) and February 2020 (two storms) along the south coast of the UK (Met Office, 2014; 2020a,b). Pescaroli and Alexander (2018) classified such events as compound, interacting and interconnected risks and elaborated on their complex dynamics. From coastal resilience perspective, it is crucial to be aware of the compound risks from successive storms and to develop appropriate mitigation strategies accordingly. Successive storms are especially dangerous as the most severe UK floods occur when storm surges combine with high spring tides (Haigh et al., 2016). Since spring tides reach their maximum approximately every 14 days, successive storms occurring over prolonged periods are more likely to result in at least one hazardous extreme sea level event.

9. Conclusions

This research was motivated by the observation of long-duration storm surges generated along the south coast of the UK in October–November 2023 due to a chain of storms. A hybrid method consisting of analysis of oceanic and atmospheric data, field surveys, and numerical modelling were employed to study the storm chain and explain their generation mechanisms and associated storm surges. Main

findings are:

- Three storms were detected in the period from 27th October to 5th November consisting of an unnamed storm (27–30 October), Storm Ciarán (2–3 November) and Storm Domingos (4–5 November). Among these three storms, Ciarán was the strongest one.
- Among the examined stations, the average maximum air pressure drop was 42 hPa during Ciarán and 23 hPa during Domingos. The maximum wind speed and wind gust during the entire storm chain period (27th October–5th November) were 99.8 km/h and 149.6 km/h, respectively.
- The three storms altogether generated an average storm surge duration of 10.5 days based on data from 16 locations. This storm chain generated one of the longest recorded storm surges along the south coast of the UK.
- The average maximum storm surge amplitude was 92 cm for Ciarán and 74 cm for Domingos based on data from 16 tide gauge stations across the English Channel. The maximum storm surge was due to Ciarán, and was recorded in Jersey (south of English Channel) with a height of 167 cm.
- Runup survey was conducted to correlate our modelling and analysis with actual conditions on the ground. We surveyed runup heights of 4.1 m in Chesil Beach and 2.1 m in West Bay. Empirical runup models were successfully adapted to reproduce the observed runup heights. Such empirical models are crucial for storm hazard mitigation and resilience.
- We successfully modelled the storm surges generated by this storm chain through numerical modelling employing a three-level nested grid system on the actual bathymetry of the English Channel. Sensitivity analysis of our numerical modelling by considering the impacts of tides and waves revealed that they have highly spatially-dependent impacts, and can increase maximum surge amplitude.

Fig. 17. Results of depth-averaged momentum budget analysis at the eastern English Channel during the two storms Ciarán and Domingos. The top and middle panels show the time series of momentum changes Δp due to the astronomical tides, that is, $\Delta p = p_{S+P+T} - p_{S+P} - p_T$ where p is different momentum terms in Eq. (7). Note that Δp is the spatial averages at locations where the maximum storm surge increased by tides over 20 cm in the eastern English Channel (see Fig. 16). The bottom panels show the balance of Δp when the positive and negative changes in storm surges by tides at Dover reached their maxima (dz^+ and dz^- , respectively).

Fig. 18. Ranking of: (a) minimum MSLP, and (b) maximum 10-m wind speed, during storm Ciarán (31st October–5th November 2023). Ranking is given relative to: (a) minimum MSLP and (b) maximum wind speed, both in the period 1940–2022. Hatched areas denote 2nd and 3rd lowest MSLP (a) and highest wind speed (b). Path of the 2023 Storm Ciarán centre is given with yellow circles.

- A meteotsunami with an amplitude of 17–23 cm and a period of 11–40 min was identified in the sea level time series. It was likely triggered by smaller-scale atmospheric pressure disturbances associated with Storm Ciarán.

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Sources of all data used in this study are listed in the body of the article and in the Acknowledgments section. Additional data can be provided upon writing to the corresponding author.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mohammad Heidarzadeh: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jadranka Šepić:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Takumu Iwamoto:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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